

Farming Open LLMs for Biomedical Question Answering

Dimitra Panou^{1,2}, Alexandros C. Dimopoulos^{1,3}, Martin Reczko^{1,*}

¹ Institute for Fundamental Biomedical Science, Biomedical Sciences Research Center “Alexander Fleming”, 34 Fleming Street, 16672 Vari, Greece

² Department of Informatics and Telecommunications, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, 15784 Athens, Greece

³ Hellenic Naval Academy, 18539 Piraeus, Greece

panou@fleming.gr, dimopoulos@fleming.gr, reczko@fleming.gr

* Corresponding author

Abstract. A large number of performant, open Large Language Models (LLMs) are continuously appearing. Here we deploy a selection of these for embedding and retrieval of documents and snippets as well as retrieval-augmented generators to answer biomedical questions within the BioASQ competition. Dense retrieval based on distances between dense representations obtained by LLM embeddings of the corpus and the question and hybrid sparse/dense methods result in higher mean average precisions compared to traditional sparse retrieval methods. In the exact answer category, which is processed using open LLMs in a zero-shot approach, our submission shares one first place in the last batch of the BioASQ 12b competition.